

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Using Artificial Intelligence for secondary analysis of ZEB34A clinical trials data

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on
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(Q1) Proposal name

Using AI in trials – a ZEB34A trial sub-study

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

Retrospective secondary analysis of phase II clinical trial data.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This research involves secondary analysis of quantitative clinical trial data from case report forms (CRFs), Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) histology images, genomic sequence data (whole exome sequence and 500 gene panel data).

No qualitative data will be used for this analysis.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

Data in this project comes from a single source – the ZEB34A clinical trial, managed by the University

Existing data from closed clinical trials including clinical trial and genomic sequence data, currently held in bespoke databases and as files within the University Clinical Trials Unit (CTU). This data will require export and pseudonymisation to allow project researchers to work on it.

Biobank data held with the National Cancer Biobank (NCB) held within bespoke databases and as files.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Data from this project will be derived from the following:

- ~1000 pseudo-anonymised patient health record data exported from production databases. Data volume estimated ~10s-100s Mb.
- ~1000 Genomic data samples in VCF formats from gene panel and whole-exome sequencing. WES estimated total ~50Gb of data.
- ~1000 H&E slide images in TIFF and other proprietary formats (Zeiss, Mirax and Olympus). Estimated total volume ~200Gb.
- Software containers and software code. Estimated volume ~200Gb.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Researchers on the project will predominantly be working with copies of data already collected for other purposes and already subject to stringent clinical trials or biobank records management procedures.

Software containers and code will be developed and stored using industry standard approaches (e.g. Dockerfile and Definition scripts for virtualised environment using Docker and/or Singularity and GitHub or equivalent for software code and scripts).

The compute and storage solutions this project will use are hosted for us by the University's high-performance computing department and have extensive experience with deploying enterprise-quality computer solutions.

Project specific ad-hoc groups will be created within the University Active Directory structure to manage ownership and staff access to both the compute and storage systems this project will utilise.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Standard metadata, produced as per the ZEB34A clinical trial will be utilised for this secondary analysis study.

The metadata files uniquely identify each data object within the study CRFs and will be replicated and structured consistently across the sub-study to enhance its discoverability and reusability.

Details of the methodologies used to characterise and analyse the primary data will be recorded. All outputs from this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources designed for this purpose (e.g. GitHub).

The project will follow the UK Data Service guidelines for describing qualitative data.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All data for the ZEB34A sub-study will be stored as anonymised datasets, and may only be accessed or shared by the Clinical Trials Unit in their anonymised format for future research, in compliance with the initial terms of consent by the trial participants.

Document records and data used for secondary analyses are required by the University to be retained for 5 years after the last action is completed in accordance with the BBSRC Statement on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice.

Data will be stored long-term during the data retention

period on the University's Research Data Repository (RDSS) following standard data retention processes for this institution. This facility provides all projects with up to 5 terabytes of storage on the centrally managed Research Data Store. Within this data store, copies of the raw, unprocessed datasets will be stored, plus algorithms and copies of test datasets.

Anonymised datasets and accompanying metadata will also be made publicly available on repositories such as the National Institute of Health's repository, Gene Expression Omnibus.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Our work plan explicitly states our aim to democratise and share the outputs from our artificial intelligence work in terms of best practice guidance, professional training and compute environments suitable for federated analytics. Following publication, we intend to publish the data from this sub-study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly within scientific journals at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date. All source data will be made publicly available through the UK Data Service. Methodologies, including statistical analyses and scripts and results will be published in open-access scientific journals.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Data from this research will be made available on the ISRCTN Registry, citing the main ZEB34A clinical trial. ISRCTN registry attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number, which maybe referenced in future citations.

The project proposal has a strong theme around the democratisation of AI technologies. As such the outputs from our third parties at the earlier possible opportunity and form a key output from the project. This project has identified several routes for dissemination of outputs across the wider research networks from applicants of this work.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Publishing of the data will be under Creative Commons Attribution Licence conditions and metadata of a sufficient standard to enable users to reanalyse the data and understand its origin and use.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

The primary datasets are under the Data Controllorship of the University CTU, whereby the University is the designated Sponsor and data controller.

Access to these primary datasets may be achieved through negotiation and contact with the University CTU.

(Q14) Secondary use

Due to this project being a secondary analysis of clinical trial data, data controllership and consent model, this project is limited for additional analysis, and the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Data provided as part of the initial clinical trial ZEB34A was compliant with the requirements of ICH-GCP and the clinical trials regulations, following all Clinical Trials Unit policies and procedures.

Data will be stored on secure systems with access only to the project team.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

All data available to researchers on this project, whilst being derived from patients, will have undergone pseudonymization by staff within the Clinical Trials Unit and/or National Cancer Biobank and will be released to the project after satisfying their information security and governance procedures.

Data Scientists working on the data will not be members of staff who have access to the pseudonymization key, and therefore will not be able to re-identify patients as per the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement.

Data will be stored on within the RDSS systems which have been designed by our advanced research computing partners to be ISO27001 compliant and capable of holding data with a Highly Confidential classification.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University provides all projects with up to 5 terabytes of storage on the centrally managed Research Data Store Service to host data for long term storage in compliance with funding requirements and to allow public access to data where governance and researchers require. Provision of funding throughout the retention period of this data was secured through the funding application and will be ring-fenced by the University's research Data Storage Service to ensure appropriate retention of the data.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

This data management plan (DMP) has been produced using the BBSRC template DMP and will be reviewed annually, or in times of change, or if any issues relating to compliance are observed. It is the responsibility of members of the project management team (notably the data scientist and Senior Statistician) to maintain this DPM as a living document throughout the duration of the research project

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University holds an up-to-date, ISO 14001 certified environmental management system, which has been held continuously since 2012. This covers good practice and continual improvement of the University's environmental aspects including energy, procurement, pollution, travel, waste, water and biodiversity.

(Q20) Responsibilities

All members of the project team (including academic applicants, project partners and appointed posts) will have responsibility for project oversight, data management, metadata creation, data security and data quality assurance.

They will be assisted by other units within the University, including our core information security and governance team, data managers with the Clinical Trials Unit, Information Security and Information Governance experts within the University.